

OPTIMIZATION OF SURGICAL TACTICS AND CHEMOTHERAPY IN PULMONARY ECHINOCOCCOSIS

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Annotation

Relevance. One of the most common causes of parasitic pulmonary invasions encountered in surgical practice is echinococcosis. According to the World Health Organization, approximately 3 million people worldwide are affected by echinococcosis each year. The Republic of Uzbekistan is also considered an endemic region for this disease.

Aim of the study was to improve the effectiveness of treatment in patients with pulmonary echinococcosis through the use of albendazole as a local germicidal agent.

Materials and Methods. The clinical study included 87 patients diagnosed with pulmonary echinococcosis.

Results. The comparison group consisted of 45 patients with pulmonary echinococcosis who received albendazole according to the standard treatment regimen. The main group included 42 patients with pulmonary echinococcosis who, in the postoperative period, received oral albendazole at a dose of 5 mg/kg per day in combination with local antiparasitic (contact) treatment of the residual cavity walls using the developed technique.

Conclusion. The combined use of low-dose systemic albendazole with its topical application as a local germicidal agent according to the proposed method demonstrated a pronounced anti-recurrent effect in the treatment of pulmonary echinococcosis.

Keywords: pulmonary echinococcosis, albendazole, local germicidal agent, recurrence, prevention.

Relevance. One of the most common causes of parasitic invasions encountered in surgical practice is echinococcosis [4, 7]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 3 million people worldwide are affected by echinococcosis annually. The Republic of Uzbekistan is also classified as an endemic region for this disease. Due to climatic, geographical, social, and

economic factors, various zoonotic foci with different levels of epizootic activity exist in the country. Therefore, the incidence of echinococcosis in humans is directly related to the intensity of epizootic processes in these foci. Echinococcosis can affect various organs in the human body, with pulmonary echinococcosis being the second most common localization after the liver [1, 5, 9]. Pulmonary echinococcosis is characterized by a severe clinical course, delayed diagnosis, and a high risk of complications. Progressive cyst growth may lead to compression of lung tissue, disruption of bronchial communication, cyst rupture, and secondary infection, all of which pose a serious threat to the patient's life. Currently, surgery remains the primary treatment modality for pulmonary echinococcosis [3, 6]. However, surgical intervention is associated with significant risk factors, including the patient's general condition, cyst size and localization, presence of complications, and history of previous surgical procedures. In addition to oral administration, albendazole is also used as a local contact germicidal agent, particularly in minimally invasive surgical procedures [2, 8]. Typically, albendazole or hypertonic solutions are instilled into the cyst cavity; however, these approaches may increase the risk of purulent complications.

Aim of the Study. To evaluate the clinical efficacy and safety of combined systemic administration of low-dose albendazole with a locally applied germicidal technique for the prevention of recurrence following surgical treatment of pulmonary echinococcosis.

Materials and Methods. To reduce adverse effects associated with oral or injectable albendazole administration-particularly systemic toxicity and side effects-we developed a combined chemotherapeutic approach involving local contact antiparasitic treatment of pulmonary tissue with albendazole and oral administration of albendazole at a low dose (5 mg/kg/day). The clinical effectiveness of this approach was evaluated. The study was conducted between 2022 and 2025 in patients treated for pulmonary echinococcosis at the Kashkadarya Regional Phthisiology and Pulmonology Center. The effectiveness of the proposed method in preventing postoperative recurrence of pulmonary echinococcosis was assessed. The essence of the proposed technique lies in ensuring a targeted local effect by placing a sterile sponge soaked in albendazole solution into the pulmonary echinococcal cyst cavity or onto the surgical wound surface. Tamponade of the pathological focus using a Spongostan-based sponge provided prolonged and directed local germicidal activity. For this purpose, a sterile sponge measuring $7 \times 5 \times 1$ cm was soaked in 50 ml of 0.9% sodium

chloride solution containing albendazole at a concentration of 10%. This approach ensured direct exposure of the drug to the pathological focus while minimizing systemic effects. Additionally, patients were recommended to receive postoperative oral albendazole at a low dose of 5 mg/kg/day. This comprehensive approach aimed to prevent recurrence of pulmonary echinococcosis through the synergistic effect of local and systemic therapy. The 10% concentration of albendazole was considered effective and safe, as confirmed by numerous experimental and clinical studies conducted by Erzurumlu et al. [6]. The comparison group included 45 patients with pulmonary echinococcosis who received albendazole according to the standard regimen (10–12 mg/kg/day, not exceeding 800 mg/day) in three 28-day courses with 14-day intervals. The main group consisted of 42 patients who, in the postoperative period, received oral albendazole at a dose of 5 mg/kg/day in combination with local contact antiparasitic treatment of the residual cyst cavity walls using albendazole.

Results. After discharge, all patients were placed under scheduled medical follow-up. Follow-up included chest radiography and computed tomography, as well as regular clinical monitoring. Additionally, biochemical blood parameters were assessed every 6 months for 1.5–2 years. Analysis of the results revealed recurrence of pulmonary echinococcosis in 5 patients (11.1%) in the comparison group, predominantly within the first year of follow-up. No recurrence cases were observed in the main group during the entire observation period. Furthermore, no local (purulent complications, infection of the residual cavity) or systemic (hepatotoxicity, allergic reactions) adverse effects were observed in patients treated using the proposed method. The dynamics of biochemical parameters confirmed preservation of overall physiological stability and the safety of the treatment approach. The obtained data demonstrate the high clinical efficacy of the developed combined approach in preventing recurrence of pulmonary echinococcosis.

Conclusion. Despite the relatively limited sample size, the results of this study demonstrate that the combination of systemic administration of low-dose albendazole with locally applied germicidal treatment using the developed methodology is effective in preventing recurrence of pulmonary echinococcosis. The proposed approach not only reduces the risk of disease recurrence but also minimizes the likelihood of local and systemic complications and is well tolerated by patients. These findings indicate that this method represents a promising and practical strategy for postoperative prophylaxis in pulmonary echinococcosis.

References

1. Ahumada Topete VH, Garcia Martin MO, Hernandez Silva G, Parra Vargas AJ, Martinez Briseño D, Castillejos Lopez M, Perez Orozco FB, Choreño Parra JA, Sevilla Gutiérrez KD, Recinos Carrera EG, Fernandez Plata R. Pulmonary manifestations and clinical management of echinococcosis in a low-endemic region of Mexico: a 15-year retrospective cohort study at a tertiary hospital. *Tropical Medicine and Health*. 2025 Mar 10;53(1):37.
2. Akbulut S. Post-treatment Follow-Up, Surveillance, and Prevention Strategies in Hydatid Disease. In *Hydatid Disease: Diagnosis, Treatment and Follow Up Strategies* 2025 Oct 1 (pp. 177-186). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
3. Bakinowska E, Kostopanagiotou K, Wojtyś ME, Kiełbowski K, Ptaszyński K, Gajić D, Ruszel N, Wójcik J, Grodzki T, Tomos P. Basic operative tactics for pulmonary echinococcosis in the era of endostaplers and energy devices. *Medicina*. 2023 Mar 10;59(3):543.
4. Goussard P, Eber E, Mfingwana L, Nel P, Schubert P, Janson J, Pitcher R, le Roux C. Paediatric pulmonary echinococcosis: A neglected disease. *Paediatric Respiratory Reviews*. 2022 Sep 1;43:11-23.
5. Li Y, Liu Y, Guo Q. Pulmonary echinococcosis mimicking tuberculosis in a child from a dual-endemic region: a case report. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*. 2025 Apr 7;13:1562829.
6. Kakamad FH. Thoracoscopic capitonnage for pulmonary hydatid cysts: the predictors of prolonged air leak. *Frontiers in Surgery*. 2025 Oct 28;12:1664976.
7. Mfingwana L, Goussard P, van Wyk L, Morrison J, Gie AG, Mohammed RA, Janson JT, Wagenaar R, Ismail Z, Schubert P. Pulmonary Echinococcus in children: A descriptive study in a LMIC. *Pediatric Pulmonology*. 2022 May;57(5):1173-9.
8. Shaprinskiy V, Verba A, Formanchuk T, Formanchuk A, Chernychenko O. Surgical treatment of echinococcosis of the liver and its complications. *Wiad lek*. 2022 Jan 1;75(1 pt 2):244-50.
9. Yang Q, Wang L, Shi Y, Liu S, Fan D, Wu B, Duan Y, Xin C, Duan L. Case Report: Pulmonary echinococcosis misdiagnosed as bronchogenic pulmonary cysts. *Frontiers in Medicine*. 2025 Mar 17;12:1533124.

